

FABRICATION OF COPPER LINE PATTERN BY VARIOUS SCANNING SPEED USING NANO PARTICLE DEPOSITION SYSTEM (NPDS) AND THE STUDY ABOUT ITS CONDUCTIVITY FOR DIRECT PRINTING TECHNOLOGY

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Nano particle deposition system(NPDS) is a novel powder deposition system based on the Cold spray and Aerosol deposition. Contrary to Cold spray and Aerosol deposition, NPDS can apply to deposit both metallic and ceramic powders on various substrates at room temperature, so it gives an alternative solution for low temperature processing technologies.[1-3] The velocity of the powders in NPDS is controlled by the Stand off Distance(SoD), throat size of the nozzle and power of pressure.

Here, SoD is defined as the distance between substrate and the upper side of nozzle. Deposition at room temperature is possible by NPDS. Because when powders collide with substrate, its kinetic energy transform into the thermal energy. A schematic of the NPDS is shown in Fig.1.

The purpose of this study is to form a conductive micro patterned line using 100-nm sized copper nanopowders on silicon wafer using NPDS equipped with micro nozzle 100- μm sized hole by varying scanning speed. Copper is relatively superior to the other metals in view of thermal and electric conductivity. Among the various fields, Ink-jet printing technology is already used for patterning micro circuit of copper. This technology can eliminate the mask patterning process to lower its cost compared to conventional lithography process. However, this printing technology requires several solvents to disperse the copper powders. NPDS is dry-coating equipment which does not require any solvent and it is a relatively simple process even compared to ink-jet printing technology. Furthermore, NPDS can fabricate the micro patterning of copper using micro nozzle.

This geometric nozzle fabricated by the Deep Reactive Ion Etching (DRIE) induces the fluidic flow to dramatically accelerate by method of the

fluidic compression and expansion. [4] Fig 2. shows 3-dimensional figure of 100- μm size of hole nozzle observing by FE-SEM.

After nano-particles deposition, the thickness and morphology of deposited copper line by various scanning speed was investigated by Alpha-step and FE-SEM, respectively. Fig 3 shows the morphology of the deposited copper line at 300- μm of SoD by

5 $\mu\text{m}/\text{sec}$ of scanning speed. The deposited copper lines on the silicon substrate by various scanning speed were sintered at 350°C for 4 hr in hydrogen atmosphere and then its electrical properties were measured by I-V curve.

Deposited copper line by 5 $\mu\text{m}/\text{sec}$ of scanning speed showed ohmic contact which reflect its conductivity and its resistivity was approximately $1.68 \times 10^{-4} \Omega\text{cm}$. However, samples fabricated 8 $\mu\text{m}/\text{sec}$ and 10 $\mu\text{m}/\text{sec}$ of scanning speed do not show conductivity properties. This result indicates that when deposition was conducted at low scanning speed, both thicknesses and densities of the deposition lines were more improved. Fig 3. shows that the sample fabricated at 5 $\mu\text{m}/\text{sec}$ was sintered well.

In this study, the possibility of the new printing technology for making copper line at room temperature was confirmed using NPDS. Therefore, because NPDS of novel printing technology can not only fabricate micro patterning of copper but also deposit ceramics at dry condition, it is expected to be applied to various devices such as capacitor and solar cell.

Fig.1. Schematic of nano particle deposition system

Fig.2. Schematic of the fabricated 100μm nozzle used in NPDS

Fig.3. Picture of deposited copper lines on silicon wafer using 100--μm hole at 5μm/sec

References

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